

Measures administered in the study were:

- 1) PCL-5 for PTSD assessment
- 2) Hopkins Symptom Checklist for depression and anxiety (HSCL25)
- 3) the Patient Health Questionnaire-15 (PHQ15) for somatic symptom measurement
- 4) the Perceived Stress Scale-14 (PSS14) for stress assessment
- 5) War and Adversity Checklist-26 for measuring traumatic events
- 6) 11 supplementary questions. This self-developed measure is based on 11 years of clinical experience with this population to capture traumatic events that are specific to this population which are:

1. Did your family member die during the chemical attack in Halabja?
2. Did your family member go missing during the chemical attack in Halabja?
3. Did your family member go missing and later return?
4. Were you missing during the chemical attack and left alone?
5. Did you lose your sight or fainted during the chemical attack?
6. Did you harm someone else or leave behind any family members during the attack in order to survive?"
7. Were you injured and bleeding during the chemical attack in Halabja?
8. Did you feel unable to think clearly or feel confused during the chemical attack?
9. Have you faced any obstacles or threats from unknown persons?
10. Did you receive the necessary treatment when you arrived in Iran?
11. Did you witness bodies in groups during the chemical attack?